

World News of Natural Sciences

An International Scientific Journal

WNOFNS 20 (2018) 176-181

EISSN 2543-5426

The evaluation of the in-vitro antimicrobial activity of *Alangium salvifolium* (Linn)

Mohammad Nadeem Khan

Sos in Biotechnology, Bastar University, Jagdalpur - 494001 (C.G.), Inda

E-mail address: sahani.nadeem35@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Finding healing power in plants is an ancient idea, and people of all continents and civilization have been using plants in one form or the other for poultices or as decoctions. *Alangium salvifolium* (Linn), family Alangeaceae, is a tree that grows in the wild throughout India. The plant has been used in the Indian traditional system of medicine for skin diseases (e.g. leucoderma), articular diseases, and anti-inflammation, anti-poisonous, anti-pyretic, and anti-emetic requirements. However, no scientific evidence is available regarding its antimicrobial activity. An investigation of *Alangium salvifolium* as an antimicrobial activity agent is the objective of our present study. The ATCC culture used in this study was collected from department of Microbiology, G.M.C., Bhopal (M.P.). Shade dried crude powder (200 grams) of seed of *Alangium salvifolium* was separately extracted with methanol in a soxhelt apparatus. The Antimicrobial activities were then studied by applying the Disc-Diffusion method. Our results indicate that the observed antimicrobial activity of the fraction appears to be due to unknown secondary metabolites in it. H.P.L.C. (high performance liquid chromatography) and chemical studies may, thus be useful in analyzing the presence of unknown secondary metabolites in the fractions.

Keywords: Antimicrobial activity, disc diffusion, soxhelt apparatus, secondary metabolites, *Alangium salvifolium*

1. INTRODUCTION

Finding healing power in plants is an ancient idea. People of all continents and civilization used plants in one form or the other like poultice or decoction. Due to problem like adverse effects, limited life span and misuse of traditional antibiotics, effects are currently

underway to look for products of natural origins and studies on traditional knowledge. Presently there is an increasing interest in the use of plants Microbicides because of the necessity of finding safer microbicides and the need for preventing environment degradation. *Alangium salvifolium* (Linn) family Alangeaceae is a tree/herb which grows in the wild throughout the india¹. The plant has been used in the Indian traditional system of medicine in skin diseases (eg: leucoderma), articular diseases, anti-inflammation, anti-poisonous, anti-pyretic, and anti-emetic². However no scientific evidence is available regarding its antimicrobial activity. Investigations of *Alangium salvifolium* as an antimicrobial agent are the objectives of our present study.

2. MATERIALS & METHODS

Preparation of plants (Seed) extract

Shade dried crude powder (200 grams) of seed of *Alangium salvifolium* was extracted with methanol in a soxhelt apparatus separately³. The extract was concentrated and the resin was precipitated by adding acidulated water and filtered. It filtrate was evaporated up to dryness, the dry filtrate weighted and re-dissolved in milliliter water yield a solution containing 50 mg/ml of the extract. Finally 500 ug concentration were prepared as per standard procedure and stored in amber-colored storage vials at 4-5 °C until used for the experiment

Micro-organisms

The ATCC culture used in this study were collected from department of Microbiology, G.M.C., Bhopal (M.P.). The ATCC strain used in this study were *Bcillus cereus* (1178), *Bacillus subtillis* (6633), *Staphylococcus aureus* (29737), *Staphylococcus epidermis* (6538), *E. coli* (10536), *Klebsiella pneumonia* (10031), *Pseudomonas aeru* (9027), *Streptococcus faecalis* (8083), *Micrococcus luteus* (9341), *Bordetella bronchiseptica* (4617)

Antimicrobial activity

The Antimicrobial activities were studied by Disc Diffusion Method. The antimicrobial activity was examined in the terms of zone of inhibition produced after overnight incubation at 37 °C and compared with standard drugs.

3. OBSERVATION

The antimicrobial activity of the water soluble fraction of *Alangium salvifolium* extract against different ATCC bacterial strain is shown in Table 1. It can be seen from the table no-1 that all the isolated strain of *Bacillus cereus* (1178), *Bordetella bronchiseptica* (4617), *Klebsiella pneumonia* (10031), and *Pseudomonas aeru* (9027) and *Bacillus subtillis* (6633) were sensitive to ASE. A rough estimate of relative potencies were made from the zone of inhibition and the following conclusions emerge which apply only to 'Doses' of ASE and reference drugs in the discs. The fraction of ASE was as active as Streptomycin against *Staphylococcus aureus* but was less effective then Erythromycin and Gentamycin against

Klebsiella Pneumonia 70% of B. subtilis 50% Pseudomonas aeru. Cultured were sensitive to ASE. The activity being comparable to that of contrimaxozole amongst the other ATCC cultured, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Staphylococcus epidermis* were uniformly sensitive to ASE, While 80% *Bacillus cereus* 40% of micrococcus luteus and 70% *E. coli* were inhibited by the ASE fraction.

Table 1. Comparative antimicrobial activity of water soluble fraction of ASE extract against microorganisms.

S.no.	Bacterial species (ATCC no.)	Num. of plate			Zone of inhibition in mm.				
			R	S	ASE5 00ug	Contrimaxozole 2ug	Gentamycin 200ug	Stuptomycin 100ug	Erythromycin 10ug
1	<i>Bcillus cereus</i> (1178)	10	10	-	8-20	0-15	-----	0-25	8-20
2	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> (6633)	08	6	-	7-15	0-14	-----	----	0-9
3	<i>S. aureus</i> (29737)	5	3	2	8-12	0-20	0-12	0-25	----
4	<i>S. epidermis</i> (6538)	6	5	1	8-10	0-15	-----	0-12	8-12
5	<i>E. coli</i> (10536)	25	20	5	8-12	-----	-----	----	-----
6	<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i> (10031)	14	9	5	6-8	0-10	0-20	-----	7-10
7	<i>Pseudomonas aeru</i> (9027)	11	11	-	7-13	0-8	-----	0-11	0-24
8	<i>S. faecalis</i> (8083)	18	12	6	4-9	0-12	-----	----	8-12
9	<i>Micrococcus luteus</i> (9341)	15	13	2	7-24	----	0-10	0-12	6-12
10	<i>Bondretella bronchiseptica</i> (4617)	16	16	-	6-10	0-17	-----	0-25	-----

S = Sensitive, R = Resistance
(Figure in parenthesis indicate total number of culture studied)

Antimicrobial activity of ASE was compare to that of Contrimaxozole, Gentamycin for *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *Pseudomonas aeru* and Erythromycin, streptomycin in remaining

micro-organisms. *Strepto faecalis* resistant to ASE was sensitive to contrimaxozole and erythromycin but *E. coli* sensitive to ASE was found to be resistant to all other antibiotics tested. *Staphylococcus aureus* resistant to ASE was sensitive to contrimaxozole Gentamycin and streptomycin, while the growth of resistant *Bacillus subtilis* was inhibited by erythromycin.

In summary, the effect of ASE was comparable to that of contrimaxozole against *S. aureus*, *S. faecalis* *S. epidermis*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *Pseudomonas aeru.* to streptomycin against micrococcus luteus and kanamycin against *E. coli*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Bacillus subtilis*. Its activity against *Bordetella bronchiseptica* was less than that of erythromycin and tetracycline.

Fig. 1. *Alangium salviifolium* (L.f.) Wangerin

4. DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

Secondary metabolites from medicinal plants exhibit a range of biological activities including antimicrobial, antioxidant, insecticide, herbicidal, immunosuppressive or stimulator, nerve tonic³⁻⁸. They have been extracted from plants for centuries, however, their exploitations yet to be fully realized³. The biosynthesis of these metabolites is controlled genetically and affected strongly by the environmental influences that may be biotic or abiotic^{9,10} as a result there are fluctuations of these secondary metabolites such as Alkaloids, glycosides, volatile oil and steroids⁸. Developing countries like India, in particular have an urgent need for such extraction since they depend for greater extent upon plant derived compounds. Medicinal plants in Western region of Madhya Pradesh are highly useful as drug. Many species are being lost which might have yielded useful products to mankind and profit to the industry especially Pharmaceutical industry. Antimicrobial effects of hydrophobic and hydrophilic extracts of roots and shoot, seed leaves and whole plants (panchang) of the medicinal plants were tested against gram positive /gram negative bacterial species. In view

of these hydrophilic characteristics of this active principle present in the plants .the observed antimicrobial activity of the fraction appears to be due to unknown secondary metabolites in it. H.P.L.C. (high performance liquid chromatography) and chemical studies analyzing the presence of unknown secondary metabolites in the fractions ¹¹⁻¹⁷.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to staff member of department of microbiology and specially Mr. Tauffeq Khan for media preparation and strain collections

Reference

- [1] Hamill; JD, Parr AJ, Rhodes MIC, Robins RJ and Walton NJ, New routes to Plant Secondary metabolites. *Biotechnology*, 1987, 5, 500-504.
- [2] Fowler MW, New approaches to plants as sores of medicinal compounds, *Pharm L*. 1980, 224, 39-40.
- [3] Deans SG and Svoboda KP, Biotechnology and bioactivity of culinary and medicinal plants. *AgBiotech News and Information* 1990 Vol. 2 No. 2 pp. 211-216 ref. 99
- [4] Cragg GM, Plant products as antimicrobial agents, *Clin. Microbial Rev.* 199, 12, 564-582.
- [5] Recio MC, Review of some antimicrobial compounds isolated from medicinal plants reported in literature, 1978-1988, *Phytochem. Rev.* 1989; 117-125.
- [6] Sikarwar, R.L.S., Bajpai, A.K. and Painuli, R.M. 1994. Plants used in Veterinary Medicines by Aborigines of Madhya Pradesh, India. *Int. J. Pharmacog.* 32(3): 251-255.
- [7] Debbarma M, Pala NA, Kumar M, Bussmann RW, *Afr J Tradit Complement Altern Med.* 2017 Jun 5; 14(4): 156-168. doi: 10.21010/ajtcam.v14i4.19.
- [8] Mahida Yogesh , Screening of plants for their potential antimicrobial activity against Staphylococcus and Salmonella spp. *NPR* 2007; 6,4; 301-305.
- [9] Khalid S, Alzan, Rizvi HA and Badar Y, A antimicrobial and phytochemical Screening of some Pakistani medicinal plants. *J fore. Pharm. Gaziuni*, 1998, 15: 7-18.
- [10] Jain PP, Sori RK, Desmusk SK. A fatty acid oil seeds of forest orgin as antimicrobial agents, *India Forest.* 1987: 113, 279-299.
- [11] Ahamed I , Beg AZ, Antimicrobial and phytochemical studies on 45 Indian medicinal plants against multi –drug resistant human pathogens. *J. Ethnopharmacol*, 2001, 74: 113-123
- [12] Sikarwar, R.L.S. 2002 Floristic Diversity in Chambal Ravines of Madhya Pradesh. *J. Econ. Tax. Bot.* 26(1): 55-65.
- [13] Sikarwar, R.L.S., Brijlal and Maheshwari, J.K. 2002. Traditional Phytotherapy among the Tribals in Raigarh district of Chattisgarh. *J. Non. Timb. For. Prod.* 9 (1&2): 22-25.

- [14] Sikarwar, R.L.S. 2002. Utilization and Conservation of Medicinal Plants in Narainpur, Chhattisgarh State, India. *Jour. Trop. Med. Pl.* 3 (2): 213-218.
- [15] Sikarwar, R.L.S. 2002. Ethnogynaecological Uses of Plants New to India. *Ethnobotany* 14: 112-115.
- [16] Kumar, Vivek and Sikarwar, R.L.S. 2002. Observations on some rare and endangered plants of Chhattisgarh state, India. *Phytotaxonomy* 2:135-142.
- [17] Sikarwar, R.L.S., Kumar, Vivek, Rawat, A.K.S., Mehrotra, S. and Pushpangadan, P. 2003. *Radermachera xylocarpa* (Roxb.) K.Schum.- An endangered and interesting tree of Central India. *Phytotaxonomy* 3: 32-34.